

POLITICAL SCIENCES

PLANNING AND IMPLEMENTATION OF PUBLIC POLICIES: AN ANALYSIS OF THE STRATEGIC VISION OF THE MINISTRY OF INTERIOR OF TURKEY

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Abstract

This study aims to examine the processes of planning and implementing public policies within the framework of the Republic of Turkey Ministry of Interior's Strategic Plan for 2019–2023. Accordingly, the 2019–2023 Strategic Plan constitutes a significant document that defines the Ministry's strategy for fulfilling these responsibilities. The plan outlines a set of objectives to enhance the performance of the Ministry of Interior, improve efficiency, and ensure the safety and well-being of citizens. In this research, the SWOT analysis method was employed to analyze the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats within the framework of the Ministry's strategic objectives. Key areas such as border management, counter-terrorism, road safety, and security pathways were highlighted, and the effectiveness of practices in these areas as well as the challenges encountered were examined in detail. According to the findings of the study, projects supported by European Union funds and national resources significantly contribute to strengthening border security and surveillance capacity. The implementation of modern technological systems presents opportunities in terms of counter-terrorism and border security, while the high costs and time-intensive nature of these processes pose challenges in practice. Additionally, the potential adverse impacts of global and regional developments on Turkey's border security and public order may threaten the achievement of strategic objectives. The study concludes that strengthening financial resources, enhancing personnel capacity, improving inter-agency coordination, and making monitoring and evaluation mechanisms more effective are essential for the successful implementation of the Ministry of Interior's strategic plan. Lastly, it is recommended that financial resources be strengthened, personnel capacity be increased, and inter-agency coordination be improved to ensure the effective implementation of the Ministry's strategic plan. Furthermore, the activation of monitoring and evaluation mechanisms is of critical importance to prevent deviations that may occur during the planning processes.

Keywords: Turkey, Ministry of Interior, Strategic Plan, SWOT Analysis.

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Introduction

The effectiveness of modern states is measured by the quality of the services they provide to their citizens and the extent to which these services align with societal expectations. In this context, the planning and implementation of public policies have become key indicators of a state's governance capacity. Public policies encompass the managerial methods and practices developed to address current societal issues, enhance social welfare, and set strategic goals for the future.

In Turkey, although the planning and implementation of public policies are undertaken by various governmental institutions, the role of the Ministry of Interior in this process is particularly noteworthy. The Ministry shapes the state's approach to its citizens by implementing its strategic vision in areas such as public order, security, local governance, and social solidarity. In this regard, analyzing the strategic vision of the Ministry of Interior provides a significant framework for understanding the dimensions of planning and implementing public policies.

This study aims to analyze the strategic vision of Turkey's Ministry of Interior to gain deeper insights into the processes of planning and implementing public policies. It will discuss the extent to which this vision aligns with societal priorities, institutional objectives, and implementation strategies within the framework of current policies. Moreover, it seeks to provide critical insights into the fundamental factors that must be considered for the effective implementation of public policies. The core focus of this examination will be on the impact of components such as strategic planning, institutional coordination, and monitoring and evaluation on the effectiveness of public policies.

Finally, the study aims to serve as a guiding resource for researchers, managers, and decision-makers working in the fields of public policy and strategic management.

Strategic Planning

Strategic planning is a process undertaken to identify an organization's long-term goals and determine the necessary steps to achieve these goals. It involves developing strategies and plans to achieve optimal results by leveraging the organization's resources and capabilities [1,2].

The Importance of Strategic Planning: Strategic planning is vital for the future of an organization. This process helps outline the steps required to achieve or-

ganizational goals and ensures their realization. Additionally, strategic planning assists organizations in utilizing resources effectively and addressing future uncertainties [3]. The strategic planning process typically involves the following steps:

Analysis: The internal and external environments of the organization must be analyzed. Internal analysis involves evaluating the organization's resources and capabilities, while external analysis assesses economic, social, political, and technological factors that may influence the organization [4].

Goal Setting: Long-term goals of the organization must be identified. These goals should reflect the organization's vision, mission, and values [5].

Strategy Development: Strategies needed to achieve organizational goals must be determined. These strategies should be designed to deliver optimal outcomes by utilizing the organization's resources and capabilities [6].

Planning: Steps necessary for implementing the strategies must be planned. This includes addressing aspects such as timelines, budgets, resource allocation, and coordination with other organizational operations [7].

Implementation: The required steps for executing the plans must be undertaken. This involves utilizing organizational resources, human resources, and technologies to bring the strategies to fruition [8].

Monitoring and Evaluation: The final stage of the strategic planning process involves monitoring and evaluating organizational performance. This stage measures the organization's progress towards its goals, assesses the effectiveness of strategies, and introduces corrective measures when necessary [9,10].

Key Elements for the Success of Strategic Planning: The success of strategic planning depends on the following factors [11].

Leadership: The success of strategic planning hinges on the determination and leadership skills of the organization's leadership [12].

Resources: The organization must have the necessary resources for the strategic planning process [13].

Capacity: The strategic planning process should align with the organization's capacity, including its size, expertise, and operational capabilities [14].

Alignment with Goals: The strategic planning process must align with the organization's goals, reflecting its vision, mission, and values [15].

Strategic planning helps organizations determine the steps necessary to achieve their future goals. This process aids in the effective use of resources and in addressing future uncertainties. To successfully complete the strategic planning process, organizations must consider leadership, resources, capacity, and alignment with their goals [16,17].

The Ministry of Interior plays a critical role in ensuring internal security, public order, and the well-being of citizens in Turkey. Thus, the strategic plan defining the Ministry's approach to fulfilling these responsibilities is a crucial document. The plan outlines a series of objectives to enhance the performance of the Ministry of Interior, improve efficiency, and ensure the safety and well-being of citizens [18].

Maintaining public order and ensuring security: This objective aims to preserve public order and safeguard citizens' safety by enhancing the operational capabilities of the police, gendarmerie, and coast guard units, modernizing security measures, and improving efforts to combat crime and terrorism [19].

Ensuring Internal Security: This goal targets activities such as combating terrorist organizations, addressing smuggling and organized crime, enhancing border security, and managing refugees to ensure internal security [20].

Providing Better Services to Citizens: This goal seeks to improve service quality by modernizing police departments, utilizing technology in delivering security services, and establishing an effective communication strategy to meet citizens' needs for safety and peace [21].

Enhancing Organizational Efficiency: This goal focuses on improving the performance of the Ministry of Interior and its affiliated institutions, streamlining internal processes, strengthening human resources management, and ensuring the efficient use of resources [22].

The Ministry of Interior's 2019–2023 Strategic Plan serves as a significant roadmap for ensuring Turkey's internal security and public peace. The plan demonstrates the Ministry's commitment to achieving its objectives, delivering better services, and enhancing internal efficiency [23]. While pursuing these goals, the Ministry will engage more actively with the public, considering citizens' views and suggestions in planning and decision-making processes [24].

Ministry of Interior 2019–2023 Strategic Plan

- *“In the field of border management, collaboration and coordination with relevant institutions, EU member states, and neighboring countries will be enhanced.*

- *Projects financed by European Union funds and national resources will strengthen control and surveillance capacities at land and sea borders, as well as at border gates. Training activities targeting stakeholders will be increased.*

- *A modern and technological border security system will be established at land and sea borders. These systems are expected to make significant contributions to the country's counter-terrorism efforts, the prevention of smuggling, the reduction of irregular migrant crossings, and the enhancement of border security.*

- *Security roads prioritized by the Governorships as designated by the Ministry will be addressed.*

- *The construction of security roads will be carried out by Metropolitan Investment Monitoring and Coordination Boards (YIKOB) in metropolitan cities and by Provincial Special Administrations in other provinces.*

- *Inter-agency cooperation will be increased within the scope of coordinating and monitoring security roads” [23].*

Findings

- *“The capacity of personnel from relevant institutions operating at border gates, border lines, and areas beyond borders must be enhanced in line with evolving situations and regulations concerning integrated border management and practices. Global and regional*

developments pose risks and threats to Turkey's borders, given the country's geopolitical location.

- *In the context of counter-terrorism, the maintenance, repair, and enhancement of damaged roads used by security units—responsible for ensuring the safety, security, and public order of citizens living in rural areas—must be undertaken. Furthermore, new roads that meet technical standards need to be constructed, and traffic safety must be improved in regions affected by topographic and climatic conditions” [23].*

Requirements

- *“To ensure the effective implementation of integrated border management, the technical, practical, and regulatory capacities of personnel serving in the field of border management must be developed.*

- *Physical security measures at borders are required to combat terrorism, prevent smuggling, curb irregular migrant crossings, and ensure border security.*

- *Adequate funding is needed to ensure the timely completion of security roads” [23].*

The implementation of this plan is of vital importance for realizing the strategic vision of the Ministry of Interior and safeguarding Turkey's internal security. Therefore, the Ministry must act with the cooperation and participation of all its employees, stakeholders, and citizens to ensure the successful execution of the plan. Additionally, it is crucial to identify, monitor, and measure priorities aligned with strategic goals to minimize potential issues during the implementation process [25].

Method

This study aims to examine the planning and implementation dimensions of public policies within the framework of the 2019-2023 Strategic Plan of the Republic of Turkey Ministry of Interior. To understand the effectiveness of the Ministry's strategic vision, SWOT analysis techniques were employed.

Research Design

The research was designed as a document-based study, adopting the content analysis method. The 2019-2023 Strategic Plan document available on the official website of the Ministry of Interior, along with other related official documents, served as the primary data source. These documents were evaluated using the

SWOT analysis method (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats) in alignment with the purpose of the study [26].

Data Collection

The data utilized in the study were obtained from the following sources:

Strategic Plan Document: The 2019–2023 Strategic Plan document of the Ministry of Interior constituted the primary data source for the study.

Official Reports and Publications: Other official documents and activity reports published by the Ministry were reviewed.

SWOT Analysis Data: Open data accessible from public sources and literature on strategic objectives were utilized during the analysis process.

Data Analysis

The collected data were analyzed within the framework of the strategic objectives of the Ministry of Interior through the following steps:

SWOT Analysis: The strengths and weaknesses of the Ministry, as well as environmental opportunities and threats, were evaluated. Document-based data were thoroughly examined for this analysis.

Conceptual Framework: Strategic planning theories and approaches were compared with the goals and strategies defined by the Ministry.

Evaluation of Strategic Practices: Factors influencing the success of the strategic plan's implementation (e.g., resource allocation, stakeholder participation, and monitoring and evaluation mechanisms) were analyzed.

Comparative Analysis: The Ministry's strategic plan was compared with the strategic plans of other public institutions with similar objectives and with examples of international best practices.

Ethical Principles

All data used in this study were obtained from open sources, and no access to private information was involved. The research was conducted in compliance with scientific ethical principles.

With this methodological approach, the study examines the effects of the Ministry of Interior's strategic plan on the effective planning and implementation of public policies and provides significant insights regarding this plan.

Findings

Table 1.

	Strengths	Weaknesses	Opportunities	Threats
Strategic Plan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Developing "cooperation and coordination with EU member states and neighboring countries in border management" provides a significant opportunity for border security. - Projects financed by European Union funds and national resources aim to strengthen "control and surveillance capacities at land and sea borders." - Establishing a modern and technological border security system at land and sea borders offers significant opportunities for counter-terrorism, preventing smuggling, and enhancing border security. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -"Security road construction works will be carried out by YİKOB in metropolitan cities and by Provincial Special Administrations in other provinces." Therefore, there may be uncertainties regarding financing and management. - The establishment of modern technological systems for border security can be costly. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Increasing training activities for stakeholders can enhance awareness regarding border management. - Enhancing inter-agency cooperation for the coordination and monitoring of security roads can lead to more effective border management. - The implementation of a modern technological border security system could enable Turkey to play a more effective role in counter-terrorism, preventing smuggling, and securing borders. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Lack of cooperation and coordination in border management could pose a threat to border security. - Financial and management problems related to security road construction could hinder timely completion, weakening border security.

According to Table 1, the strengths include the enhanced cooperation and coordination with EU member states and neighboring countries in border management, which provides a strategic advantage for border security. Additionally, projects financed by EU funds and national resources aim to strengthen control and surveillance capacities at land and sea borders. Establishing a modern technological border security system creates significant opportunities for counter-terrorism, smuggling prevention, and overall border security. The weaknesses highlight uncertainties and high costs associated with certain implementations. For instance, security road construction is managed by Investment Monitoring and Coordination Boards (YİKOB) in metropolitan cities and by Provincial Special Administrations in other provinces. However, the lack of clarity regarding financing and management in these processes

poses challenges. Moreover, the installation of modern technological systems for border security can be financially burdensome. Opportunities emphasize the importance of increasing training activities for stakeholders to raise awareness about border management. Enhancing inter-agency cooperation for the coordination and monitoring of security roads presents a significant opportunity for more effective border management. Furthermore, implementing modern technological border security systems could enable Turkey to play a more active role in counter-terrorism, smuggling prevention, and border security. Threats include the potential lack of cooperation and coordination in border management, which could pose a significant risk to security. Additionally, financial and management issues related to security road construction may delay project completion and weaken border security.

Table 2.

	Strengths	Weaknesses	Opportunities	Threats
Findings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Developing the capacities of relevant institution personnel working at border gates, borderlines, and hinterlands regarding integrated border management and practices provides a significant advantage for Turkey's border security. - Security units ensuring the safety, public order, and security of rural residents play an effective role in counter-terrorism. - Improving the quality of newly constructed roads and maintaining and repairing existing ones in accordance with technical standards offers a significant opportunity to enhance Turkey's road safety. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Enhancing the capacities of relevant institution personnel may involve high time and cost requirements. - Financial uncertainties may arise regarding projects aimed at improving the quality and maintenance of roads built to technical standards. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -In light of global and regional developments, Turkey has the potential to play a more effective role in border security. - Security units ensuring the safety, public order, and security of rural residents could be further empowered to play a more effective role in counter-terrorism. - Constructing new roads and upgrading existing ones to meet technical standards could lead to significant advancements in road safety in Turkey. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Global and regional developments regarding border security may pose a threat to Turkey's border security. - Financial uncertainties in road construction projects and the improvement of existing infrastructure may hinder their timely and effective completion.

According to Table 2, the strengths include the development of the capacities of relevant personnel working at border gates, borderlines, and hinterlands concerning integrated border management and practices, which offers a substantial advantage for border security. Furthermore, security units play a critical role in counter-terrorism by ensuring safety, public order, and security in rural areas. Additionally, constructing new roads and improving existing ones according to technical standards significantly enhances Turkey's capacity in road safety. The weaknesses highlight challenges, such as the time and cost associated with enhancing personnel capacities and uncertainties regarding the financing of infrastructure projects. Improving the capacities of relevant institutions can impose a significant financial and temporal burden. Similarly, uncertainties

in funding for new road construction and maintenance projects can limit the effectiveness of these efforts. The opportunities emphasize Turkey's potential to play a more active role in border security and counter-terrorism in the context of global and regional developments. The current capabilities of security units operating in rural areas can be further strengthened through additional capacity building. Moreover, constructing and upgrading roads to meet technical standards offers significant progress in road safety. The threats include the risk posed by global and regional developments that may negatively impact Turkey's border security. Additionally, financial uncertainties in projects for road construction and infrastructure improvement could delay or obstruct the timely and effective completion of these initiatives.

Table 3.

SWOT Analysis of the Ministry of Interior's 2019–2023 Needs

	Strengths	Weaknesses	Opportunities	Threats
Needs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Ensuring the effective implementation of integrated border management provides a significant advantage for Turkey's border security. - Implementing physical border security measures is essential for playing an effective role in counter-terrorism, smuggling prevention, and border security. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - "Enhancing the technical, practical, and regulatory capacities of relevant institution personnel" may involve high costs and time requirements. - Failure to allocate the necessary funds for timely completion of security roads could lead to uncertainties in the implementation of road construction projects. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Integrated border management could enable Turkey to play a more active role in counter-terrorism, smuggling prevention, and border security. - Physical border security measures could enhance Turkey's border protection capacity, strengthening national security and supporting regional stability. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -The inability to allocate sufficient financial and time resources for enhancing personnel capacities may reduce the effectiveness of these processes. - Budgetary constraints in security road projects could delay their completion, jeopardizing border security.

According to Table 3, the strengths include the effective implementation of integrated border management, which provides a crucial advantage for Turkey's border security. Additionally, implementing physical border security measures is vital for enabling effective efforts in counter-terrorism, smuggling prevention, and border security. The weaknesses highlight the high costs and time requirements associated with enhancing the technical, practical, and regulatory capacities of relevant institution personnel. Furthermore, the failure to allocate adequate funds for the timely completion of security road projects could create uncertainties in project

management and completion processes. The opportunities suggest that adopting integrated border management practices could enable Turkey to take on a more active role in counter-terrorism, smuggling prevention, and border security. Implementing physical border security measures can enhance border protection capacity, bolstering national security and contributing to regional stability. The threats include the risk of reduced effectiveness due to insufficient financial and time resources allocated for enhancing personnel capacities. Additionally, insufficient funding for security road projects could delay their completion, posing risks to border security.

Table 4.

SWOT Analysis of Border Management

	Strengths	Weaknesses
Opportunities	-Global and regional developments may enable Turkey to play a more active role in border security.	-Capacity development may require significant time and financial resources.
Threats	-Global and regional developments may pose a threat to Turkey's border security.	-Uncertainties may arise, particularly regarding financing.

As shown in Table 4, border management is a critical issue for Turkey's security. This analysis highlights key opportunities, such as enhancing cooperation and coordination with EU member states and neighboring countries, strengthening control and surveillance capacities at border gates, and establishing border security systems, which offer significant advantages for

Turkey's border management. However, the development of capacity may require considerable time and financial resources. Additionally, global and regional developments could pose threats to Turkey's border security, while uncertainties in funding are also considered a potential risk. Therefore, when planning its border

management efforts, the Ministry of Interior must consider these strengths, opportunities, weaknesses, and

threats to ensure an effective and comprehensive strategy.

Table 5.

	Strengths	Weaknesses
Opportunities	- Security units ensuring the safety, public order, and security of rural residents could be equipped with the necessary capabilities to play a more active role in counter-terrorism.	-Capacity development may require significant time and financial resources.
Threats	- Global and regional developments in counter-terrorism may pose a threat to Turkey's efforts in this area.	-Uncertainties regarding financing could arise.

As shown in Table 5, counter-terrorism is critical for maintaining safety, public order, and security across the country. This analysis identifies opportunities, such as the potential for security units ensuring the safety and public order of rural residents to play a more active role in counter-terrorism with the necessary resources and capabilities. However, capacity development may require substantial time and financial resources, representing a significant weakness. In addition, global and

regional developments in counter-terrorism could pose threats to Turkey's efforts in this domain, while uncertainties regarding financing are also identified as a potential threat. Therefore, when planning its counter-terrorism efforts, the Ministry of Interior must consider these strengths, opportunities, weaknesses, and threats to develop a robust and comprehensive strategy.

Table 6.

	Strengths	Weaknesses
Opportunities	-The construction of new roads and the improvement of existing roads to meet technical standards provide a significant opportunity for enhancing road safety in Turkey.	-Capacity development may require significant time and financial resources.
Threats	-Uncertainties regarding financing could arise.	---

As shown in Table 6, road safety is crucial for reducing traffic accidents and ensuring smooth traffic flow nationwide. This analysis identifies opportunities such as the construction of new roads and the enhancement of existing roads to meet technical standards, which represent a significant opportunity to improve Turkey's road safety. However, the development of ca-

capacity may involve substantial time and financial resources, posing a major weakness. Additionally, uncertainties in financing are considered a threat that could hinder progress in road safety initiatives. Therefore, when planning its road safety efforts, the Ministry of Interior must consider these strengths, opportunities, weaknesses, and threats to create an effective and sustainable strategy.

Table 7.

	Strengths	Weaknesses
Opportunities	-Prioritizing security roads as determined by the governorships, enhancing coordination, and implementing security road construction projects provide significant opportunities for improving Turkey's security roads.	-Capacity development may require substantial time and financial resources.
Threats	-Uncertainties regarding financing could arise.	---

As shown in Table 7, security roads are vital for maintaining safety, public order, and security across the country. This analysis identifies opportunities such as prioritizing security roads determined by governorships, enhancing coordination, and implementing road construction projects, which provide significant benefits for Turkey's security infrastructure. However,

weaknesses include the high time and cost requirements associated with capacity development. Additionally, uncertainties regarding financing pose a threat to the successful implementation of security road projects. Therefore, when planning initiatives for security roads, the Ministry of Interior must consider these strengths, opportunities, weaknesses, and threats to ensure effective and well-coordinated strategies.

Table 8.

	Strengths	Weaknesses
Opportunities	-Implementing physical border security measures is essential for playing an effective role in counter-terrorism, smuggling prevention, and border security.	-Capacity development may require significant time and financial resources.
Threats	-Global and regional developments may pose a threat to Turkey's border security.	-Uncertainties regarding financing could arise.

As shown in Table 8, physical border security measures are crucial for maintaining safety, public order, and security across the country. This analysis highlights that implementing these measures provides a significant opportunity for counter-terrorism, preventing smuggling, deterring irregular migration, and ensuring border security. However, capacity development could involve high costs and significant time requirements, representing a notable weakness. Additionally, global

and regional developments may pose threats to Turkey's border security, while uncertainties related to financing are also identified as a critical threat. Therefore, when planning efforts regarding physical border security measures, the Ministry of Interior must carefully consider these strengths, opportunities, weaknesses, and threats to devise effective and sustainable strategies.

Table 9.

Integrated Border Management SWOT Analysis		
	Strengths	Weaknesses
Opportunities	-Enhancing the capacities of personnel from relevant institutions involved in border management, increasing training activities in line with evolving situations and regulations regarding integrated border management and practices, offers significant opportunities for Turkey's integrated border management.	-Capacity development may require substantial time and financial resources.
Threats	-Global and regional developments may pose a threat to Turkey's border security.	-Uncertainties regarding financing could arise.

As shown in Table 9, integrated border management is a critical issue for Turkey's security. This analysis highlights that enhancing the capacities of personnel from relevant institutions and increasing training activities aligned with evolving situations and regulations regarding integrated border management provide significant opportunities for improving Turkey's border management capabilities. However, capacity development could involve significant time and financial resources, presenting a major weakness. Additionally, global and regional developments may pose threats to Turkey's border security, while uncertainties regarding financing are also identified as a critical threat. Therefore, when planning efforts related to integrated border management, the Ministry of Interior must carefully consider these strengths, opportunities, weaknesses, and threats to develop an effective and comprehensive strategy.

Conclusion

This study examined the processes of planning and implementing public policies within the framework of the Republic of Turkey Ministry of Interior's 2019–2023 Strategic Plan. Core responsibilities of the Ministry, including internal security, maintaining public order, and ensuring the well-being of citizens, constitute the main pillars of the strategic plan. The findings obtained through SWOT analysis reveal the strengths, opportunities, weaknesses, and threats associated with the Ministry's strategic vision.

According to the research findings: **Border Management:** The establishment of modern technological border security systems creates significant opportunities for counter-terrorism and preventing smuggling. However, capacity development processes pose challenges in terms of time and cost. **Counter-Terrorism:** The safety of rural residents can be supported by enhancing the capacities of security units. Nevertheless, global and regional threats present risks to these efforts. **Road Safety:** Constructing new roads and improving existing infrastructure provide solutions for traffic safety, but financial uncertainties may delay the com-

pletion of projects. **Security Roads:** Security road projects prioritized by governorships can be effectively completed through enhanced inter-agency cooperation. Projects financed by European Union funds and national resources contribute significantly to strengthening control and surveillance capacities at land and sea borders. Moreover, the establishment of modern border security systems and the improvement of security roads offer significant progress potential in areas such as counter-terrorism and border security. However, timely allocation of financial resources is essential to ensure the completion of these projects.

Despite the opportunities, the weaknesses and threats encountered during implementation are noteworthy. Financial issues and high costs associated with capacity development processes pose significant barriers to achieving strategic goals. Additionally, delays in completing border management and security road projects may create risks for both local and national security. Global and regional security dynamics represent another critical threat influencing Turkey's strategic vision. **Recommendations for Effective Implementation**

To ensure the effective implementation of the strategic plan, the following recommendations are proposed:

Strengthening Financial Resources: The sustainable use of EU funds and national budgets should be ensured to guarantee the continuity of projects.

Capacity Development Activities: Training programs should enhance the technical, practical, and regulatory skills of personnel working in areas such as border management and security roads. Modern technologies should be utilized in this process.

Enhancing Inter-Agency Coordination: Stronger collaboration mechanisms should be established among public institutions to achieve strategic objectives.

Activating Monitoring and Evaluation Mechanisms: The implementation process of the strategic plan should be regularly monitored, and swift solutions should be developed for potential deviations.

In conclusion, the Ministry of Interior's 2019–2023 Strategic Plan plays a critical role in ensuring Turkey's internal security and enhancing citizens' well-being. Successful implementation of the plan requires effective leadership, resource allocation, and inter-agency collaboration. Collaboration among all stakeholders and continuous review of planning processes are essential for realizing Turkey's vision for internal security.

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